

The effects of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD

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Abstract

Introduction: Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is considered a commonly diagnosed neuropsychiatric disorder in childhood. Normally, the behaviour of the students in the classroom could be directly related to the teacher's interventions with them. **Purpose:** The aim of this research was to analyse the effect, after an attempted educational intervention by the teacher on a student who is diagnosed with ADHD and to then assess whether or not their behaviour is affected after such an interaction has taken place. **Method:** Six Physical Education (PE) teachers and six students, who were diagnosed with ADHD and ranged from the third grade level until the sixth grade level of Primary Education, were observed for 42 full PE classes. In total, 681 behavioural conducts and 397 teaching interventions were analysed. At the end of the study, teachers were interviewed for an average of 65 minutes to conclude my findings. **Results:** Students with ADHD showed three categories of desirable behaviour (basic social skills and being able to manage their feelings, skills related to the teacher and skills related to their peers) and four categories of undesirable behaviour (hyperactivity, impulsiveness, attention deficit, and other behaviours: disobedience, screams, tantrums, attention-seeking, disruptive behaviour towards others, and boredom). Teachers mostly used intervention techniques, such as praise and attention, known as Behavior Modification Techniques (BMT) to maintain or increase desirable behaviour. In contrast, BMT was used to reduce or eliminate negative behaviour and those most commonly used by teachers were: direct verbal instructions, expulsion and punishment. Two effects were identified: behaviour either persisted (32%) and behaviour was modified (68%). **Discussion/Conclusion:** The type of BMT used is more effective when the behaviour is desirable. In undesirable behaviours the type of BMT was considered insignificant, since in both cases, the behaviour tends to change. The analysis of the effect of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD is valuable information for PE teachers, in order to redefine their interventions. As a consequence, future research will aim to examine the strategies implemented by PE teachers when dealing with ADHD students in order to increase desirable behaviours and reduce undesirable ones.

Keywords: Primary Education, Attention Deficit Disorder, Hyperactivity, Behaviour, Teachers.

Introduction

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is considered a commonly diagnosed neuropsychiatric disorder in childhood, but the prevalence of the condition is not widely acknowledged in many countries (Catalá-López et al., 2012).

Barkley (2006) highlights that, in students with ADHD, three ideas or concepts must be distinguished. These concepts are: inhibition (inability to wait, inability to stop what you are doing, etc.), self-regulation (ability to regulate one's own impulses) and executive functioning (self-control).

Also, in most cases, children with ADHD have associated disorders, for example: affectivity problems (mood or anxiety disorders), learning disorders, school failure, conduct disorders and, in one way at a time more significantly, motor coordination disorders (Artigas-Pallarés, 2003).

Every human being, during his childhood, observes, imitates and learns infinity of behaviours of his relatives or similar. These behaviours are categorized as desirable behaviours, defined as appropriate habits, in accordance with today's society, with what is expected of the person; and other opposite behaviours, known as undesirable behaviours, which are associated with a set of attitudes and skills contrary to those expected of the individual (Merino, 2008). What the same author states in the educational field is that the learner is not able to distinguish what he 'should' or 'should not' learn, especially when we talk about boys and girls between 6 and

12 years old (p. 72). It is then here that the figure of the teacher as a mediating agent arises, a figure proposed by Feuerstein and Jensen (1980).

This theory is based on Feuerstein's (1980) theory of structural cognitive modifiability and is considered a practical approach that also implies the ability to improve the intelligence of the recipient subject through the timely mediation of an adult. That is, the stimuli emitted by the environment are transformed by a mediating agent (the father, the mother, the brother, the teacher or others). The mediating agent, using his intentions, his culture and his emotions, selects and organizes the most appropriate stimuli for the receiver, in such a way that, in future situations, he will be able to identify, classify and organize a set of stimuli relevant to the difference of others less important.

In a similar vein, behaviour modification programs stand out, which aim to promote change through psychological interventions (Pignato, Patania, Schembri and Sgrò, 2019) in order to contribute to the improvement of student behaviour. They do not intend to change the personality of the subject, but rather the habits considered unsuitable or inappropriate (Merino, 2008).

The purpose of this study was to analyse the effect after educational intervention on the conduct of students with ADHD, by assessing whether or not their behaviour changes after such intervention has taken place. To do this, it was necessary to combine the scientific knowledge discussed below and to use a table of contents listing the behaviours which were of interest (Table 1 and Table 2, published in a previous study of Labrador, Hernández, and Inglés, 2019).

The version of the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 4th edition revised* (DSM-IV-TR) used between 2002 and 2013 and the new version (DSM-V) used from 2013, describes a 'feature of ADHD (as) a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that is more frequent and severe than is typically observed in individuals of a similar level of development' (APA, 2002, p. 97). Manifested behaviours include: behavioural disorders, sleep disorders, lack of self-control, aggression, low motor coordination, depression, anxiety or lack of respect for rules (Carriedo, 2014; Harvey and Reid, 2005).

In Spain, it has been claimed that 6.8% of students aged between 5 and 15 are diagnosed with ADHD (Catalá-López et al., 2012). According to Arnett, Pennington, Willcutt, DeFries and Olson (2015), in the US, epidemiological investigations indicate significant sex differences in prevalence of ADHD, in favour of males. While the American Psychiatric Association [APA] (2013) states that there is no global consensus on the prevalence of ADHD in children, meta-regression analysis have estimated the worldwide prevalence at between 5.29% and 7.1% (Polanczyk, Willcutt, Salum, Kieling, and Rohde, 2014).

At school, students with ADHD tend to have stressful and conflictual interactions with their peers and also have difficulties with self-discipline (Salla, Galéra, Guichard, Tzourio, and Michel, 2017). They often display lower levels of academic engagement and motivation than students without these difficulties, a situation that has a negative impact on their academic outcomes (Volpe, DuPaul, DiPerna, Jitendra, Lutz, Tresco, and Junod, 2006).

Furthermore, 'children with ADHD represent a significant number of students in school systems worldwide who often experience difficulties in performing fundamental movement skills' (Harvey, Wilkinson, Pressé, Jooper, and Grizenko, 2014, p. 205).

Students with ADHD have difficulty paying attention in non-selective activities and are hyperactive and impulsive (Turner and Burne, 2016). They present uncontrolled reactions and unstable personality, which hinders the learning, the work, recreational activities and engaging in social environments. These difficulties may be accentuated in unstructured environments (Mulas, Mattos, Hernández-Muela, and Gandía, 2005).

ADHD has been studied from medical and psychological perspectives, but in Spain the educational aspect has been largely ignored (Jin, Li, Du, Coghill, Au, and Zhong, 2016). Students with ADHD also have comorbid disorders such as: affective problems (mood disorders or anxiety), learning disorders, school failure, behavioural disorders and increasingly Developmental Coordination Disorders (Gillberg et al., 1997; Gustafsson et al., 2010; Kadesjö and Gillberg, 1998). In spite of the high prevalence of ADHD in the educational context, Anderson, Watt, Noble and Shanley (2012) note that teachers lack knowledge about the disorder. Moreover, 'although it is common for physical education teacher, education majors to graduate with knowledge and skills grounded in scientific principles, many do not develop the ability to manage problematic student behaviours' (Lavay, Henderson, French, and Guthrie, 2012, p. 195).

Commonly, the behaviour of the students in the classroom has been related to the intervention of the teacher (Mordal Moen et al., 2019). For this reason, beginning in the mid-1970s, the majority of courses aimed at helping teachers in relation to student behaviour, were focused almost exclusively on behaviour modification techniques' (Jones and Jones 1990, p. 10). Years later and along this same line, the work of Fernández and De Barros (2015) addresses the type of teaching intervention from an inclusive approach based on the desirable and undesirable behaviours of students (Gaintza and Castro, 2020).

It is thought that the type of educational intervention or pedagogical actions (O'Leary, Longmore, and Medcalf, 2020; Tolgfors, 2019) can have a direct impact on the behaviour of students with ADHD, in addition, it would be influenced based on the possibilities and the environment presented by the educational centre itself (Martínez, López, López, Castro, Buñuel, and García, 2019).

DuPaul and Stoner (2004) consider that schools must contribute to adapt to the needs of students with ADHD in order to achieve the maximum possible development of their personal abilities, including: maintaining a structured and motivating environment, segmenting activities that are considered 'long' and reinforcement of desirable behaviours. Despite the fact that there is some controversy regarding the need and consequent effectiveness of the intervention based on behaviour modification techniques with boys and girls with ADHD, Fabiano, Pelham, Coles, Gnagy, Chronis-Tuscano and O'Connor (2009) and Hodgson, Hutchinson and Denson (2014), confirm solid and consistent evidence that behavioural treatments are effective in treating ADHD.

These techniques are supported by the operational methodology and are based on managing the consequences associated with student behaviour. In other words, reinforced behaviours tend to repeat themselves in the future, and unrewarded behaviours should diminish or become extinct. This fact represents a basic principle on which the behavioural model of classroom discipline is supported (Fontana, 1994).

With this in mind, the objective of this work is to analyse the effect, after educational intervention has been conducted on students with ADHD and to then assess whether or not their behaviour changes after such an intervention has taken place.

Method

This research is characterized by its exploratory nature, since, after an in-depth bibliographic review, no studies were found on the behaviour of students with ADHD in PE classes or on the analysis of teaching interventions with this type of behaviour and its corresponding effects. This study took place in educational centres (public, private or semi-private centres) of the city of Barcelona and the Maresme region. As Reinaldo, Pereira and Medeiros (2008, p. 22) affirm: 'exploratory research is carried out on a problem or research question when there are few or no previous studies in which we can search for information on the question or problem'.

Participants

A total of six PE teachers (age in years: $M = 40.33$, $SD = 4.85$) have participated in the study. All of them had more than six years of teaching experience ($M = 15$, $SD = 6.38$). The teaching staff belonged to six educational centres and have at least one student diagnosed with ADHD in their class.

Students with ADHD (age in years: $M = 9.50$, $SD = 1.12$) were eligible if they met the following criteria: (a) clinical diagnosis of ADHD made by the child's clinician, (b) students are attending fourth, fifth or sixth grade and (c) students should be taking a prescribed medication first thing in the morning (specifically methylphenidate hydrochloride – this treatment is common in people with combined ADHD). The ADHD diagnosis of each student was submitted in written format by the child's clinician and was confirmed by the Conners 3-Parent Report, where 95% of students scored in the clinical range with t scores of 65 or greater on the DSM-IV ADHD Hyperactive/Impulsive subscales.

Two different but compatible instruments of analysis have been used in this research: observation and interview (Ekholm and Dahlstedt, 2019).

Phase I: observation

To study a school-age student's behaviour, Efstratopoulou, Janssen and Simons (2012) proposed observing the child in different contexts and situations as the most valid and reliable method to establish how they interact with the teacher and their peers, and how they play, share and obey. The research reported here is a multiple case study involving six PE teachers and six students diagnosed with ADHD from fourth, fifth and sixth grades in Primary Education over a full academic year. There was one student with ADHD in each class. Students were observed in 42 full one-hour PE lessons during an academic year (with an average of seven classes at each school). The researchers adopted the role of non-participating observers based on the descriptions of Abikoff et al. (2002), since the researchers always maintained the role of external observers and remained at a sufficient distance so as to avoid involvement in the classes and to avoid distorting the dynamics of the lesson. Also, in view of the position of the researchers, it was decided to use covert observation (Carpenter and Suto, 2008); the students were aware of the general theme of the study (in order to assess their behaviour in PE classes), but not the specific details (whether the behaviour was desirable or undesirable in relation to different variables). Finally, the observation protocol comprised a standardized observation based on the use of field notes and narrative register, containing a series of descriptions and reflections received and recorded by the researcher in the natural context (Latorre, 2007).

The data from the observations was collected using an audio recorder to assist the researcher in generating a 'thick description' (Carspecken, 1999, p. 54). Additionally, detailed field notes were written during the observational period by the researcher, not in every behaviour and intervention during the class. Then, the researchers reviewed their recorded audio notes along with the field notes taken after each lesson. All the information was written by the researchers into a data sheet to be able to describe the observations for future reference.

Previously, to test the observation research instrument, two observers independently record the same number of participants during the same number of classes. An inter observer agreement (IOA) was carried out in 16 PE classes (pilot study). The IOA was calculated by dividing the small number of behaviours and interventions recorded by the largest number of behaviours and interventions and multiplying the result by 100 (Cooper, Heron, and Heward, 2007). The average IOA was 85% (range 80% - 90%). Cooper (2007) recommend

an average of 75% when multiple behaviours are evaluated by two or more observers. In order to contribute to reliability among observers, the Kappa Index (Cohen, 1960) was calculated, whose value was 0.70 with $p < 0.001$, considered substantial or important (Landis and Koch, 1977). A number of 42 PE classes (1 hour each class) were observed in six different schools ($M = 7$, $SD = 2.31$) to describe the behaviours of students with ADHD and the corresponding teaching intervention. The observation was based on the indicators in Tables 1 and 2 (student behaviour with ADHD, published in the study of Labrador, Hernández and Inglés (2019) and Figures 1 and 2 (teaching interventions), indicators published in the study of Labrador, Hernández and Inglés (2020).

Phase II: PE teacher's interview

Subsequently, the PE teachers were interviewed in order to complete the information gathered from the observation. Descriptive and inferential analyses were applied to the quantitative data, and the qualitative data underwent content analysis of the narrative registers.

The interview comprised questions posed in the context of the investigation or by other stimuli, to elicit information from the people who were being studied, which could help to resolve the central research question. The interviews were non-directive and were started by just one invitational statement: 'Let's talk about ADHD behaviour in PE classes'. The interviews lasted an average of 65 minutes.

For in-depth interviews, an interview protocol was developed based on the existing literature (Kiely and Askham, 2012) to encourage the professors to describe and evaluate their own learning experiences thoroughly and freely from their own perspectives. All the interviews were conducted face-to-face and recorded for transcription purposes. The interviews were conducted at the students' school. The interviews were transcribed immediately and the researchers reviewed each transcription with written notes from the interview while listening to the corresponding tape. In summary and coinciding with Freed and Wong (2019) that interviewing and observation are considered the best method to understand how people could describe situations, create an identity and make decisions about how to interact with the student. In this investigation, semi-structured interviews have been chosen in two specific stages of the investigation. The first stage, considered as the exploration time (during the pilot study) and in which the interview is validated based on the following points: 1) existing bibliographic review; 2) proposal of questions; 3) expert assessment; 4) administration during the pilot test; 5) analysis; and 6) reformulation of questions; and the second stage, at the end of all observations in the field work. The semi-structured interview uses a script with the most relevant and necessary information that must emerge in the speech. Along the same lines, Taylor and Bogdan (1992, p. 115) affirm that 'the guide is a reminder of the questions that must be asked about certain topics' and these, often openly and without following an established order (Massot Lafon, Dorio, and Sabariego Puig, 2004).

All the statistical procedures developed in this investigation were analysed with the "Microsoft Excel 2010" spreadsheet for Windows. And all the texts of the semi-structured interviews were transcribed and analysed with the "Nudist NVivo®" program in order to encode all the interviews of the PE teacher.

Results

Based on the desirable and undesirable behaviour of students with ADHD (table 1 and table 2), and the teachers' intervention (figures 1 and 2), which can be based on techniques to maintain or increase behaviour or based on techniques to decrease or eliminate it, the students responded with the same behaviour or modified it.

Table 1.

Desirable observed behaviours of students with ADHD in PE classes

Dimensions	Variables	Indicators	% of registers
Desirable behaviours	Basic social skills and management of feelings	Acceptance of possibilities and limitations	0.15
		Acceptance of responsibilities	1.32
		Gratitude	0.15
		Effort to comply with instructions	5.29
		Enjoyment	2.06
		Optimism	1.03
	Skills related to PE teacher	Sympathy	0.88
		Self-confidence	0.44
		Respect for decisions	0.29
		Helps teachers	0.44
	Skills related to peers	Attention to teacher comments	0.15
		Interest in what happens to the peers	0.73
		Waits his/her turn	1.62
		Helps peers	3.23
		Shares things	0.29
		Persuades others through reason, not through screams or impositions	0.15
TOTAL		19.54	

Note: Labrador, V., Hernández, F. J. & Inlgés, E. (2019). Estudio de los patrones de conducta del alumnado con TDAH en la clase de educación física. *Movimento*, 25, 615-630. doi:<https://doi.org/10.22456/1982-8918.81877>

Table 2

Dimensions	Variables	Indicators	% of registers	
Undesirable behaviours	Hyperactive behaviour	Changes or doesn't respect place in line	1.91	
		Difficulty sitting or moves excessively while doing an activity	1.32	
		Gets bored during recess	5.58	
		Does dangerous things	3.67	
	SUBTOTAL			12.48
	Impulsive behaviours	Expresses opinions out of turn and/or interrupts the conversation of others	11.01	
		Provokes others	0.44	
	SUBTOTAL			11.45
	Attention deficit behaviours	Neglects others	2.20	
		Late to class	0.59	
		Inattention	2.94	
		Seems not to hear	6.02	
	SUBTOTAL			11.75
	Disobedience	Disobeys the teacher	3.23	
		Doesn't take care of sports equipment	4.11	
Doesn't comply with the class rules		2.79		
Doesn't comply with the rules of the game		2.94		
Mocks classmates		4.26		
Screams, tantrums, requires attention		Shouts	0.88	
		Requires attention	11.16	
Other behaviours		Physical aggression	2.64	
		Verbal aggression	1.32	
		Blames others for his/her mistakes	0.29	
	Play abruptly	1.03		
	Tells lies	1.76		
	Doesn't collaborate with peers	0.59		
	Makes comments to hurt others	1.47		
	Gets angry	5.29		
	Boredom	Gets bored and complains of this boredom when doing routine or unstimulating tasks	1.91	
		SUBTOTAL		
TOTAL			81.35	

Undesirable observed behaviours of students with ADHD in PE classes

Note: Labrador, V., Hernández, F. J. & Inlgés, E. (2019). Estudio de los patrones de conducta del alumnado con TDAH en la clase de educación física. *Movimento*, 25, 615-630. doi:<https://doi.org/10.22456/1982-8918.81877>

Figure 1. Techniques to increase or maintain the behavior

Note: Labrador, V., Hernández, F. J. and Inlgés, E. (2020). Intervención Educativa sobre el Comportamiento del Alumnado con TDAH en Educación Física. *Revista Psicología del Deporte/ Journal of Sport Psychology* (in press).

Figure 2. Techniques to reduce or eliminate the behaviour

Note: Labrador, V., Hernández, F. J. and Inlgés, E. (2020). Intervención Educativa sobre el Comportamiento del Alumnado con TDAH en Educación Física. *Revista Psicología del Deporte/ Journal of Sport Psychology* (in press).

The total of registered effects, during the observation, in the behaviour presented by students with ADHD after the teaching intervention were 397. These 397 interventions were linked to 32% of behaviours that remained and 68% in behaviours that were modified.

The total number of desirable behaviours were 127. In 53.54% of behaviours, no type of intervention was registered. In 46.46% there was intervention, whose effects were distributed in 39.37% of behaviours that remained and in 7.09% of behaviours that modified.

On the other hand, the set of undesirable behaviours was 554. In 37.18% no intervention was recorded. In 62.81% there was an intervention, whose effects were split into 14.98% of behaviours that remained and in 47.83% in behaviours that were modified.

Next, a synthesis of the effects of the behaviour of ADHD students was made after the BMT used by the teachers during the PE classes. For this and considering the set of possibilities offered by the study variables, this section had considered the following relationships (table 3).

Table 3

	Techniques to increase or maintain behaviour	Techniques to decrease or eliminate behaviour
Desirable behaviours (% of registration)	37.80%	7.09%
[effect] (probability of behaviour modification)	0.0625	0.67
Undesirable behaviours (% of registration)	14.26%	47.29%
[effect] (probability of behaviour modification)	0.625	0.78

List of study variables: behaviour, BMT and effect

Thus, table 3 represents the information on the relationship between desirable behaviours, undesirable behaviours and BMT. In each case, BMT can increase or maintain behaviour, or decrease or eliminate it. Various percentages of registration and various data on the effect appeared from this relationship. When the data on the effect approaches zero, the behaviour tended to remain, on the other hand, when this data approaches one, the behaviour tended to change.

Along the same lines, it should be noted that the effects of the behaviour of the students with ADHD after the teaching intervention appeared in figure 3, differentiating whether they use techniques to increase or maintain the behaviour or techniques to decrease or eliminate it.

Figure 3. *Affects of educational intervention on the behaviour of pupils with ADHD*

As can be seen in this figure 3, significant differences appear in the effect provided by the variable desirable behaviours and the variable of undesirable behaviours in students with ADHD (value 1 and 2 of the horizontal axis), when the value approaches zero on the vertical axis it means that the behaviour tends to remain. And when it approaches 1, it shows that the behaviour tends to change.

It is noteworthy that the differences between the effects (the behaviour remains or modifies, 0 to 1 of the vertical axis) is less within the undesirable behaviours, so it is interpreted that regardless of the type of BMT used before undesirable behaviours, the effects tend to 1 (modify).

Instead, differences between effects are important within desirable behaviours, where the BMT does influence. As seen in the figure 3, when BMTs are used to decrease or eliminate them, the effect is closer to 1 (to modify it); when BMTs are used to increase or maintain them, they achieve their objective (the behaviour remains).

PE teachers' descriptions during the interviews were very similar in content to the observations. For example, when the teachers talked about the relationship between desirable behaviours and techniques that would increase or maintain them:

in reference to behaviour *overestimates their abilities*, the teacher intervenes telling them that 'we are mortal' (irony), but cites the need to also value the good behaviour like 'well ... remind him that we are mortal and that it is good enough that ... that yes ... very good with this ... but that from time to time ... it also helps me to listen ... and be calm ... but hey ... you should also value the good things you have ... (E01_Josep)

With regard to the relationship between desirable behaviour and techniques that decrease or eliminate them the effect is that the behaviour doesn't change:

...has it ever come out ... sometimes ... but he's not a child ... he doesn't do it consciously to offend his partner ... he's not 'cool', or 'cheeky' in that sense ... but yes, sometimes ... 'well I ... I'm the best!' ... but I don't think you believe it? I mean, he pulls it off ... but he doesn't pull it off ... I don't know how to say it ... you know? It gives me the feeling ... you know? That ... but then you realize you don't even believe it, because it's not really shown as such. There is no intervention here... I show him that I didn't hear him... (E06_Júlia)

In the situations when the teachers explained about the relationship between undesirable behaviours and techniques that increased or maintained them, the effect was a modified conduct.

after completing the task successfully, the teacher makes them pass group by group to show the different positions and movements in front of the whole class. When they finish the activity, the ADHD student seems to want to receive the teacher's attention and calls the teacher to pass the ball to him and receive the teacher's gaze and attention. The teacher told him, thank you. (E02_Magda)

The last relationship was about undesirable behaviours and techniques that diminish or eliminate them: during the explanations, he is commenting on everything I say ... the game, if he likes it, if he doesn't like it, if it is played like this, if I will go with you, if the couple will go with the blues, with the oranges,... or anticipates ... and is continually making that contribution. And besides, his body is ... moving: his leg is shaking, his head I don't know what ... I don't know if he can say ties, but he is moving, like in tension, to be able to start and jump ...' the teacher intervention is 'it's just that you ask him to calm down, sometimes it's with a look, sometimes it's in a gesture that you've already agreed with him of: put the dike in your mouth to say 'silence' ... or the ear to hear you ... (E03_Manel)

Thus, it could be established that the type of BMT used is more relevant when the behaviour is desirable (value 1 –horizontal axis-). On the other hand, in undesirable behaviours (value 2 –horizontal axis-) the type of BMT would be considered more insignificant, since in both cases, the behaviour tends to change.

Discussion

On the basis of Winnick's Operant Conditioning Theory approach (2010), we could focus on the effects of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD and regarding to the behaviour that remains unchanged after educational intervention, Brophy (1981) pinpoints verbal praise as a positive reinforcement of behaviour (Valentini, Rossini, Altavilla and Federici, 2019). This kind of intervention is used with the purpose of enhancing or maintaining a form of behaviour. In this research we observed that in most cases, desirable behaviour is maintained after educational intervention is applied using techniques such as praise, attention, physical contact and rewards or privileges.

García Romero et al. (2011) contend that after application of the extinction technique to desirable behaviour, such conduct may be enhanced or maintained. In this research we have observed situations in which desirable behaviour persisted after the use of techniques to diminish or eradicate particular forms of conduct. We should also point out, however, that such situations are highly uncommon.

Amado (2011) mentions that interventions based on techniques to enhance or maintain behaviour, such as praise and attention, must be opportune and descriptive. In cases where interventions are inappropriate to students' behaviour, such behaviour might persist. Consequently, non-desirable behaviour would continue to develop, even after educational intervention has taken place. In this research we noted that the relationship between non-desirable behaviour and techniques to enhance or maintain it is of little importance.

Reiber and McLaughlin (2004) defend the notion that each student with ADHD has his or her own aptitudes and form of behaviour. While conducting our study we noted that when diminishing or eradicating techniques were applied to non-desirable forms of conduct, they persist in no fewer than 57% of cases after educational intervention had taken place.

Regarding to the behaviour that modifies after educational intervention, Bados López and García Grau (2011) and Verdejo Bolonio, Herrero Navarro, Caravaca Cantabella and Escobar Solano (1999) noted that the kind of BMT most commonly applied involves instigation techniques (instructions), techniques described as long-duration temporary resources. In our research we observed that cases of desirable behaviour becoming modified after educational intervention based on BMT designed to enhance or maintain it were practically non-existent, since students with ADHD whose behaviour was already desirable will not change it after educational intervention to enhance or maintain it had been applied.

Bados López and García Grau (2011) and Verdejo Bolonio et al. (1999) mentioned that the kinds of techniques generally applied are instructions, described as long-duration temporary resources. Our research findings reveal that desirable behaviour very rarely becomes modified after educational intervention based on BMT designed to diminish or eradicate it is applied, since generally speaking teachers do not use diminishing or eradicating techniques in cases of desirable behaviour.

Santoyo and Ortega (2010) tell us that behaviour—be it desirable or non-desirable—that generates attention on the part of the teacher will tend to become either enhanced or modified. In our study we found that non-desirable forms of conduct that have become modified after educational intervention based on BMT designed to enhance or maintain them were very few, since teachers would not normally use techniques to enhance or maintain such behaviour.

Badia Martín (2002), Brophy, Coulter, Crawford, Evertson and King (1975), Heller and White (1975), Reiber and McLaughlin (2004) and Santoyo and Ortega (2010) mentioned that BMT designed to diminish or eradicate behaviour are the ones most used when it comes to attempting to modify non-desirable behaviour. Indeed, from our research we have verified that 94% of cases of non-desirable behaviour were successfully modified thanks to the application of these BMT.

Regarding, therefore, the effect of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD, Badia Martín (2002), Brophy et al. (1975), Brophy (1981), Heller and White (1975), Reiber and McLaughlin (2004) and Santoyo and Ortega (2010) referred to a set of relations that have acquired considerable importance in this research study, the most prominent of which were students' desirable conduct persists when submitted to techniques that either foment or maintain them; however, non-desirable behaviour also persisted when submitted to techniques designed to diminish or eradicate it.

On the other hand, Fernández, Tárraga and Miranda (2007), Miranda, García and Presentación (2002), Miranda, Jarque and Rosel (2006) and Miranda, Jarque and Soriano (1999) maintained that since every student with ADHD is different, the effects of educational intervention on each individual will vary accordingly. In our research we came across several relation variables, with a very low degree of representativeness, which suggest the presence of a number of unpredictable behavioural effects. These forms of behaviour are the remaining variables contemplated in our research study and mentioned in this discussion.

Conclusions

By placing this study in the context of PE classes, our purpose was to provide a source of specific information in order to contribute to knowledge of physical activity teaching, specifically of inclusive physical activity teaching. We hope therefore to have made a contribution to obtaining more comprehensive knowledge of the behaviour of students with ADHD, of interventions on the part of PE teachers and of their effects on students' behaviour.

The aims of the research were to identify the behaviour of students with ADHD by establishing a differentiation between desirable and non-desirable forms of behaviour; to describe educational interventions in response to desirable and non-desirable forms of behaviour on the part of students with ADHD; and lastly to analyse the effect on ADHD students' behaviour after they have been subjected to educational intervention.

Prominent among the different kinds of specialised knowledge we used for this study were Psychology, in an attempt to establish functional relationships between the physical world and man's basic processes, that is, cognitive, emotional and motivational; Sociology, in an attempt to explain social conduct on the basis of properties selected from social and educational structures; and Didactics, in an attempt to offer teachers a set of possibilities and alternatives to increase their competence when it comes to intervening with students.

Furthermore, by combining a quantitative methodology (observation) with a qualitative methodology (interview) we were able to identify, describe and analyse the information we gathered in a richer way.

In order to analyse the effect of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD, two effects were identified: behaviour either persists or becomes modified. The students' desirable behaviour persists (0.0625) when the teacher applies techniques that enhance or maintain behaviour, as confirmed by 37.80% of the total number of observations. Our advice to teachers would therefore be to use these kinds of techniques in the case of desirable behaviour.

On the other hand, the students' desirable behaviour tends to become modified (0.67) when the teacher applies techniques that diminish or eradicate behaviour, a situation confirmed by only 7.09% of the total number of observations. Given this circumstance, we would suggest that teachers refrain from using these kinds of techniques in the case of desirable behaviour.

Non-desirable behaviour on the part of students tends to become modified (0.625) when the teacher applied techniques that enhance or maintain forms of behaviour, as confirmed by 14.29% of the total number of observations. We would therefore propose more frequent use of such techniques, since their application tends to modify non-desirable behaviour. Nonetheless, this practical measure should be applied only when non-desirable behaviour does not disrupt the smooth running of the educational process.

And lastly, the students' non-desirable behaviour becomes modified (0.78) when the teacher applied techniques that diminish or eradicate behaviour, a situation we observed in 47.29% of cases. Even so, we would advise teachers to make less frequent use of such techniques in cases of non-desirable behaviour since, although they are effective, so are the techniques designed to enhance or maintain behaviour, whose application is perfectly feasible in such cases.

The analysis of the effect of educational intervention on the behaviour of students with ADHD means a valuable information for PE teachers in order to more precisely define their interventions. To that effect, future research will aim to examine the strategies implemented deeply by PE teachers when dealing with ADHD students in order to increase desirable behaviours and reduce undesirable ones.

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